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PHARMACOGNOSY OF AAMALAKYADI CHURNA

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Abstract

Background:

Global demand of herbal medicine is increased day by day. To compensate this demand, need more raw material, but due to less cultivation of medicinal plants it is difficult to provide needed herbs for production. Because of which the adulteration and substitution is increasing day by day. So, it is become difficult to make sure that the drug which is available in market is original or adulterated. To confirm the originality of drug there are many analysis methods are available. Pharmacognosy is one of them by which one can confirm the identity of plant and to check the impurities or adulteration in the herbal formulation. **Material & Method:** Powder microscopy of *Aamalakyadi Churna* was carried out. *Aamalkyadi Churna*¹ is an ayurvedic formulation containing *Aamalaki (Phyllanthus emblica Linn.)*², *Haritaki (Terminalia chebula Retz.)*³, *Chitraka (Plumbago zeylanica Linn.)*⁴, *Pippali (Piper longum Linn.)*⁵. Slides of each ingredient of *Aamlakyadi Churna* were prepared using required reagents and observed under the microscope. **Observation & Result:** Powder microscopy of *Aamlkyadi Churna* shows fibers, fragments of tissues, trichomes, crystals etc. **Discussion and Conclusion:** The microscopic structures which are observed in *Aamlakyadi Churna* helps in correct identification of *Aamalaki (Phyllanthus emblica Linn.)*, *Haritaki (Terminalia chebula Retz.)*, *Chitraka(Plumbago zeylanica Linn.)*, *Pippali (Piper longum Linn.)* Powder microscopy is one of the simplest methods for correct identification of herbal drug in polyherbal formulation. This helps in standardization of new drug and polyherbal formulation.

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Powder microscopy, *Phyllanthus emblica* Linn., *Terminalia chebula* Retz., *Plumbago zeylanica* Linn., *Piper longum* Linn

INTRODUCTION

The ancient Indian system of medicine known as Ayurveda is a profound science that not only emphasizes the treatment of disease, but also emphasizes staying healthy. Bhashaj in these words means Dravya - the drug used for treatment. Global demand for herbal medicines is increasing day by day. More raw materials are needed to offset this demand, but with fewer medicinal plants being cultivated, it is difficult to obtain the herbs needed for production. Hence counterfeiting and substitution is increasing day by day. So, it is difficult to make sure that the drug in the market is original or adulterated.

To confirm the originality of drug there are many analysis methods are available. Pharmacognosy is one of them by which one can confirm the identity of plant and to check the impurities or adulteration in the herbal formulation. Here, for the present study *Aamalakyadi Churna* is selected for the powder microscopy. *Aamalakyadi Churna* is mentioned by Acharya Sushruta in *Dravyasangrahaniya Adhdhyay*, and says that this *Churna* is having properties like *Sarvajwarahara*, *Chakshusya*, *Deepan*, *Vrishya*, *Kaphanashaka*, *Arochakahara*. This contain *Aamalaki* (*Phyllanthus emblica* Linn., Family-Euphorbiaceae), *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula* Retz., Family - Combrataceae), *Chitraka* (*Plumbago zeylanica* Linn., Family-Plumbaginaceae), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn., Family- Piperaceae)

AIM:

To analyse the microscopic features in the powder of *Aamalakyadi Churna*.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To assess the microscopic features such as fibres, tissues, vascular bundles, starch grains, trichomes etc. in the powder of *Aamalaki* (*Phyllanthus emblica* Linn.), *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula* Retz.), *Chitraka* (*Plumbago zeylanica* Linn) and *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.)
2. To compare the assessed features of herbal drugs with their standards mentioned in authentic reference.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Aamalakyadi Churna was used for the powder microscopy. *Aamalakyadi Churna* containing *Aamalaki* (*Phyllanthus emblica* Linn.), *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula* Retz.), *Chitraka* (*Plumbago zeylanica* Linn) and *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.) fruit of *Aamalaki*, *Haritaki* and *Pippali* and Root of *Chitraka* were collected and powdered following the standard operating procedure.

Slide preparation:

Slides of each ingredient of *Aamalakyadi Churna* were prepared separately using required reagents and observed under the microscope to assess their various microscopic features. Microscopic characters observed were compared with the standards mentioned in authentic reference

Staining agents: Safranin and iodine

OBSERVATIONS & DISCUSSION:

Table No. 1: Powder microscopic study of *Aamalaki* (*Phyllanthus emblica* Linn.)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Aamalaki</i>	Figure no.
1.	Sclereids	Fig. 1.a
2.	Fibers	Fig.1.c
3.	Epidermal cells	Fig. 1.b
4.	Pitted vessel attached with parenchyma	Fig. 1.d

5.	Pitted parenchyma	Fig. 1.d
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Table No. 2: Powder microscopic study of *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula* Retz.)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Haritaki</i>	Figure no.
1.	Fibers	Fig.2.a
2.	Epidermis	Fig.2.b
3.	Stone cells	Fig.2.c
4.	Trichome	Fig.2.d

Table No. 3: Powder microscopic study of *Chitraka* (*Plumbago zeylanica* Linn.)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Chitraka</i>	Figure no.
1.	Fragments of fibres	Fig.3.a, Fig.3.b
2.	Fragments of vessels	Fig.3.c
3.	Fragments of tangentially cut medullary rays	Fig.3.d
4.	Fragments of parenchyma	Fig.3.e
5.	Starch Grains	Fig.3.f

Table No. 4: Powder microscopic study of *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Pippali</i>	Figure no.
1.	Stone cells	Fig.4.a
2.	Starch grains	Fig.4.b
3.	Fragments of thin-walled cells	Fig.4.c
4.	Fibres	Fig.4.d

Through this present study information regarding the microscopic characters of the herbal drug can be known. For this microscopic study, powder of *Aamlakyadi Churna* was selected. The microscopic characters of *Aamlakayadi Churna* were observed which will be narrated further. Powder microscopy of *Aamalaki* shows Sclereids, Fibres, Epidermal cells, Pitted vessel attached with parenchyma and pitted parenchyma. Powder microscopy of *Haritaki* shows fibers, epidermis, stone cells and trichome. Powder microscopy of *Chitraka* shows fragments of fibres, vessels, tangentially cut medullary rays, parenchyma and starch grains. Powder microscopy of *Pippali* shows stone cells, starch grain, fragments of thin walled cells and fibres.

Standardization of compound formulations of Ayurved is quite difficult and complicated. But it is essential for assuring the quality and safety of herbal drugs thus making herbal drugs viable for the use. In this present study, powder microscopy of each ingredient of *Aamalakyadi Churna* was carried out and

their microscopic characters were noted. These characters might help in detecting impurities and exact identification of material available from the market.

Powder microscopic study of *Aamalaki* (*Phyllanthus emblica* Linn.)

Sclereid
Epidermal cells

Fig. 1.a

Fig. 1.b

Fiber
Pitted parenchyma

Fig. 1.c

Fig. 1.d

Powder microscopic study of *Haritaki (Terminalia chebula Retz.)*

Fig. 2.a

Fig. 2.b

Fig. 2.c

Fig. 2.d

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Powder microscopic study of *Chitraka (Plumbago zeylanica Linn.)*

Fig 3.a

Fig 3.b

Fiber

Fig 3.c

Fragments of vessels

Fig 3.d

Fragments of tangentially cut medullary rays

Fig 3.e

Fragment of parenchyma

Starch Grain

Fig 3.f

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Powder microscopic study of *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn)

Stone

Fig 4.a

Starch grains

Fig 4.b

Fragment
s of
thin
walled
cell

Fig 4.c

Fibre

Fig 4.d

CONCLUSION:

The current study's finding said in the identification of herbal formulation like *Aamlakyadi Churna*. As per this study an Ayurvedic formulation *Aamlakyadi Churna* have structures like stone cells, starch grains, fibres fragments of vessel, pitted parenchyma, trichomes etc.

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